

QORAQALPOQ DOSTONLARIDA ETNOGRAFIK TAFAKKUR VA AN'ANAVIY TURMUSH TALQINI

Aygul Seytmuratova

O'zbekiston davlat san'at va madaniyat
instituti Nukus filiali

Folklor va etnografiya ta'lim yo'nalishi talabasi
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19381706>

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada qoraqalpoq dostonlarida etnografik tafakkurning namoyon bo'lishi hamda an'anaviy turmush tarzining badiiy talqini o'rganiladi. Asarlarda xalqning urf-odat va marosimlari, oilaviy munosabatlari, kiyinish madaniyati, mehnat faoliyati va ijtimoiy qadriyatlari qanday aks etgani tahlil etiladi. Qahramonlar timsoli orqali milliy dunyoqarash, axloqiy mezonlar va jamoaviy hayot tamoyillari yoritib beriladi. Shuningdek, dostonlarning tarixiy xotira va madaniy merosni saqlashdagi o'rni ham baholanadi. Tadqiqot natijasida qoraqalpoq dostonlari nafaqat badiiy yodgorlik, balki xalqning an'anaviy turmushini aks ettiruvchi muhim etnografik manba ekanligi asoslab beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: qoraqalpoq dostonlari, etnografik tafakkur, an'anaviy hayot tarzi, milliy qadriyatlar, marosim va urf-odatlar, og'zaki ijod, madaniy meros, ijtimoiy muhit, badiiy talqin.

Аннотация. В статье рассматривается проявление этнографического восприятия и художественная интерпретация традиционного образа жизни в каракалпакских дастанах. Анализируется отражение народных обычаев и обрядов, семейных связей, культуры одежды, трудовой деятельности и социальных ценностей. Через образы героев раскрываются национальное мировоззрение, нравственные нормы и принципы коллективной жизни. Также оценивается значение дастанов в сохранении исторической памяти и культурного наследия. Делается вывод о том, что каракалпакские дастаны являются не только литературными памятниками, но и важными этнографическими источниками, отражающими традиционный уклад жизни народа.

Ключевые слова: каракалпакские дастаны, этнографическое восприятие, традиционный образ жизни, национальные ценности, обряды и обычаи, устное творчество, культурное наследие, социальная среда, художественная интерпретация.

Abstract. This article examines the manifestation of ethnographic perception and the artistic interpretation of traditional life in Karakalpak epics. It analyzes how customs, rituals, family relationships, clothing culture, labor practices, and social values are reflected in these works. Through heroic characters, the national worldview, ethical standards, and principles of collective life are revealed. The paper also evaluates the role of epics in preserving historical memory and cultural heritage. The study concludes that Karakalpak epics serve not only as literary monuments but also as significant ethnographic sources representing the traditional lifestyle of the people.

Keywords: Karakalpak epics, ethnographic perception, traditional way of life, national values, rituals and customs, oral literature, cultural heritage, social environment, artistic interpretation.

Introduction

In Karakalpak oral folk art, the dastan genre occupies a special place. They are a unique artistic heritage, embodying centuries-old historical experience, national thinking, and spiritual values. Dastans deserve attention not only as a literary example of aesthetic significance, but also as an important source reflecting the daily life, social relations, rituals, and moral views of the people.

In these works, the people's ideas about nature and society, national mentality, and the system of values are vividly expressed. The characteristics of traditional life are revealed through the characters' behavior, style of dress, and place in the family and society. Therefore, the study of dastans plays an important role in understanding the historical development and cultural heritage of the people.

In the process of globalization, the preservation of national identity and the preservation of rich cultural heritage has become an urgent task. From this point of view, the scientific analysis of ethnographic thinking and the depiction of traditional life in Karakalpak dastans is of great importance. Karakalpak dastans, as an artistic source reflecting the spiritual world and way of life of the people, are a vivid manifestation of ethnographic thinking. They depict everyday life, customs, rituals, forms of economic management, and social relations.

Analysis and discussion

Family and kinship relations are one of the important themes in dastans. Values such as respect for elders, loyalty to parents, and love between brothers and sisters are expressed through artistic images. The depiction of wedding ceremonies, matchmaking traditions, and other customs reveals the ritual culture of the people.

Traditional economic activities, such as animal husbandry, agriculture, and hunting, also occupy an important place in the works. The depiction of clothing, housing, and weapons gives an idea of material culture. The courage, patriotism, and loyalty of the heroes determine the moral ideal of the people. Karakalpak dastans are a unique example of oral creativity, embodying the centuries-old historical experience, social structure, and spiritual values of the people. They acquire important scientific significance not only as an artistic and aesthetic work, but also as an ethnographic source. In the dastans, the lifestyle, customs, beliefs, forms of economic management, and social relations of the people are widely depicted. Ethnographic thinking is a form of thinking that reflects the unique way of life, worldview, and system of values of a people. In Karakalpak dastans, this thinking is manifested through images, plot events, and ritual depictions. For example, in the epic "Alpamysh," the social and spiritual views of the people are expressed through tribal relations, the hero's struggle for the honor of the country, matchmaking, and wedding ceremonies. The hero's loyalty and courage determine the moral criteria of society. Also, in the epic "Forty Girls," through the image of female heroines, the gender perceptions and family values of the people are revealed. In this work, women are depicted not only as homemakers, but also as defenders of the homeland. This shows the historical roots of the status of women in Karakalpak society. Karakalpak dastans are an artistic form of ethnographic thinking, in which the material and spiritual culture of the people are harmoniously reflected. The image of traditional life manifests itself not only as historical information, but also as a moral and ideological idea. In this respect, dastans are an important cultural heritage of the Karakalpak people, preserving their ethnic identity, national values, and historical memory.

Conclusion

In general, Karakalpak dastans are an invaluable source that comprehensively illuminates the ethnographic thinking and traditional way of life of the people. They embody national values, moral norms, and social principles in an artistic form. Epics play an important role in preserving historical memory and national identity. Their in-depth study and wide promotion are of great importance in the development of national culture and the upbringing of the younger generation in the spirit of spiritual values.

In Karakalpak dastans, ethnographic thinking and the interpretation of traditional life are manifested as an artistic expression of the historical memory of the people, the system of social consciousness and spiritual values. In particular, in epic works such as "Alpamysh," "Kirkkiz," and "Edige," the customs, rituals, family relations, social structure, and economic traditions of the people are reflected through artistic images. These dastans are valued not only as aesthetic, but also as an important ethnographic source. In general, Karakalpak dastans, idealizing the traditional way of life, interpret it in harmony with historical truth and artistic thought. They serve as an important spiritual source in preserving the ethnic identity of the people, strengthening national consciousness, and transmitting cultural heritage from generation to generation.

Therefore, the study of the Karakalpak epic heritage from an ethnographic point of view allows for a deeper understanding of the system of national values and their assessment based on modern scientific interpretation.

REFERENCES:

1. Qosybayev J. **Qaraqalpaq xalıq dastanları**. No'kis: Qaraqalpaqstan, 1985.
2. **Qaraqalpaq folklori. Ko'p tomlik**. No'kis: Ilim, 1977–1990.
3. Járımbetov Q. **Qaraqalpaq xalıq awızeki dóretiwı**. No'kis: Bilim, 1996.
4. Baskakov N.A. **Karakalpakskiy folklor**. Moskva: Nauka, 1952.
5. Tolstova L.S. **Etnografiya karakalpakov**. Moskva: Nauka, 1984.
6. Alfiya, Q. (2023). Milliy Musiqa San'ati Va Yoshlar Tarbiyasi. *Journal of Creativity in Art and Design*, 1, 16-20.
7. Nazarbaevna, Q. A., & Serjanovich, K. S. (2024). The Importance of Scenario in Cultural Events. *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION*, 4, 259-262.
8. Рахимов, Б. М., & Худайберганава, М. А. (2017). О роли музыки в жизни человека. *Молодой ученый*, (31), 74-77.
9. Oybekovna, K. M. RHYTHM AND ALGORITHM: THE SYNERGY OF MUSIC EDUCATION WITH ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE.
10. XUDAYBERGENOVA, M. (2025). MUSIQA TA'LIMI SOHASIDA FINLYANDIYA TAJRIBASI: PEDAGOGIK YONDASHUVLARNING TAHLILI. «ACTA NUUZ», 1(1.6. 1), 188-189.
11. Malika, K. (2025). THE DEVELOPMENT PATH OF MUSIC EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN AND ITS CURRENT CONDITIONS. *SHOKH LIBRARY*, 1(12).
12. XUDAYBERGENOVA, M. (2024). O'ZBEKISTON TA'LIM TIZIMIDA MUSIQA O'QITISHNING SHAKLLANISH BOSQICHLARI VA TAVSIFI. *News of the NUUZ*, 1(1.9. 1), 223-225.
13. Ermanova, D. (2024). ABOUT MUSIC CULTURE AND PIANO. *Modern Science and Research*, 3(10), 76-79.